

Sparse Reservoir Topologies for Physical Implementations of Random Oscillators Networks

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Abstract

Physical implementation of recurrent neural networks is hindered by the fact that hidden units need to be trained and are often fully-connected. We propose to relieve both these constraints by adopting and improving on an oscillators-based reservoir computing model called Random Oscillators Network (RON). RON is a recurrent neural network composed by damped oscillatory units that showed excellent performance in many sequence processing tasks. RON does not require training of its hidden parameters, since it leverages on a random heterogeneous reservoir. However, the reservoir of RON depends on a fully-connected set of oscillators. In this paper, we propose 6 sparse topologies for RON and we study the performance of the model across different levels of sparsity and different numbers of hidden units. Our experiments highlight that RON can tolerate large levels of sparsity without harming its expressive power, and in most cases even outperforming its fully-connected counterpart. Also RON clearly surpasses Leaky ESN (sparse and fully-connected) and LSTM in all benchmarks. We believe RON to be an ideal candidate for the realization and the study of physical neural networks in the real world.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Neural networks**; Batch learning; *Supervised learning*.

Keywords

recurrent neural networks, reservoir computing, sparsity

ACM Reference Format:

Andrea Cossu, Andrea Ceni, Davide Bacciu, and Claudio Gallicchio. 2024. Sparse Reservoir Topologies for Physical Implementations of Random Oscillators Networks. In *4th International Conference on AI-ML Systems (AIML-Systems 2024)*, October 08–11, 2024, Baton Rouge, LA, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 9 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3703412.3703413>

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AIMLSystems 2024, Baton Rouge, LA, USA

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ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-1161-9/24/10

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3703412.3703413>

1 Introduction

In deep learning [10], sparse computation is often still implemented without relying on sparse data structures, but rather by performing dense matrix multiplications on very sparse matrices. This is mainly due to the advantage provided by co-processors like GPUs that do not really thrive on sparse multiplications, yet. However, computational efficiency is only one motivation behind the use of sparse architectures in deep learning. Implementing densely connected neural layers in physical substrates can be expensive and difficult to scale for a large number of units [4]. In this paper, we will mostly focus on oscillators-based recurrent neural networks [15] [3]. In this context, the state-update process of the recurrent network is based on a set of inter-connected damped oscillators. These oscillators can compute and adapt their parameters via back-propagation or other techniques. However, such networks can hardly be implemented in a physical substrate (e.g. mechanical oscillators) when they require hundreds or thousands of fully-connected oscillators. Such a system is far too complex to be built in the real world. Scaling down the number of oscillators and designing sparse topologies, where each unit needs not to be connected with all others, would solve all the aforementioned issues. But *at what cost?* Sparsity would give us the flexibility to create a variety of different architectures and to adapt to the constraints coming from the real world, but would the predictive performance of the resulting model still be comparable with its fully-connected counterpart?

In this paper, we answer positively to this question by designing and studying 6 sparse topologies for the Random Oscillators Network (RON) [3]: an oscillator-based recurrent network following the principles of reservoir computing. We chose topologies with very different connection patterns, to cover a wide range of possibilities. Some of them, like the ring topology, are well established in the reservoir computing literature, while some others, like the Toeplitz and the sparse orthogonal, have not been extensively investigated in reservoir computing. Our experiments prove that sparse topologies in RON are effective across different sequence processing tasks and even with a small number of hidden units. We tested different levels of sparsity and we show that, with respect to its fully-connected counterpart, sparse topologies in RON do not show any substantial decrease in predictive performance, not even with 80%/90% of sparsity in the reservoir connections.

Our main finding is that RON is an ideal candidate for the realization of a recurrent network in hardware, mainly because of its

computational efficiency due to the untrained recurrent component and its effectiveness when combined with very sparse topologies.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: in Section 2 we introduce the reservoir computing models we are interested in, namely the RON and the Leaky ESN [9], the latter acting as a baseline. We also compare RON with a fully-trained LSTM [5] recurrent model. In Section 3 we describe the 6 sparse RON topologies that we will use in the experiments. In Section 4 we provide the experimental setup as well as all the results on 3 benchmarks across different sparsity levels and different numbers of hidden units. Finally, in Section 5 we summarize our findings and we sketch some future directions, with particular attention on the physical implementation of RON-like architectures in hardware.

2 Related Works

Reservoir computing [12] is a popular solution for time-series processing that leverages on an untrained recurrent component and a trained predictor on top of it. The untrained component, called *reservoir*, is randomly initialized and kept fixed afterwards. We are interested in two families of reservoir computing models called *Leaky Echo-State Networks* (Leaky ESNs, or simply ESNs) [9] [7] [8] and *Random Oscillators Networks* (RONs) [3].

Leaky ESNs are based on a state-update equation which reads as follows:

$$h_{t+1} = (1 - \alpha)h_t + \alpha\sigma(Wh_t + W^{\text{in}}u_{t+1} + b), \quad (1)$$

where t indexes the time step, σ is the hyperbolic tangent element-wise activation function, $h_t \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the hidden reservoir state of the ESN, $u_t \in \mathbb{R}^I$ is the input vector and $W \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $W^{\text{in}} \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times N}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^N$ are respectively the recurrent state matrix, the input-to-hidden matrix and the bias. The leaky coefficient $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ controls the amount of information coming from previous time steps that is passed on directly to the next time step. When $\alpha = 1$ we obtain a vanilla ESN [8], where the previous hidden state h_t is only used inside the non-linear transformation σ . When $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, new time steps have little influence on the hidden state update.

The reservoir state is used to predict the final output \hat{y} through a linear, trained readout:

$$\hat{y}_t = W^{\text{out}}h_t, \quad (2)$$

where $W^{\text{out}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times O}$ maps the hidden space into the output space. For classification tasks, O is the number of classes, while for univariate regression $O = 1$. The entries of W^{out} are the only trainable parameters of an ESN and they can be trained either in closed-form or via iterative methods (e.g. by gradient descent-based approaches). The linear nature of the readout function allows exploitation of simple and efficient closed-form linear regression algorithms for learning the matrix W^{out} . In particular, we choose the closed-form solution with a Ridge regressor or a logistic classifier, depending on the task.

A foundational property of the ESN is the Echo-State Property [6]. This property guarantees that, after an initial transient, the reservoir state gets uniquely determined by the driving input, progressively fading the information encoded from the input in the far past. Although the ESP is a property of both the reservoir and the input together [1, 2, 13, 16], de facto, the established technique to promote the ESP is to impose $\rho_W < 1$, where ρ_W is the spectral radius of

the matrix W . This results in a necessary condition for the ESP to hold. Therefore, it is common practice to first randomly generate the recurrent matrix W , then scale W to a desired spectral radius ρ : $W = \frac{W}{\rho_W}\rho$, where $\rho < 1$ [11], and start the reservoir state at time $t = 0$ at the origin $h_0 = 0$.

Finally, the input-to-hidden matrix W^{in} is also randomly generated, and then scaled by a scalar v . Both ρ and v are treated as hyper-parameters of an ESN, to be found during model selection.

Random Oscillators Networks [3] are a family of reservoir computing models based on oscillators. The recurrent state-update equation of RON represents a discretization of a set of second-order differential equations representing an oscillatory system where each oscillator is coupled with the others via W .

The equation of an RON reads:

$$\begin{aligned} h_{t+1} &= h_t + \tau z_{t+1}, \\ z_{k+1} &= z_t + \tau(\sigma(Wh_t + Vu_{t+1} + b) \\ &\quad - \gamma \odot h_t - \varepsilon \odot z_t). \end{aligned}$$

The dynamics of an RON follows the hidden state trajectory $h_t \in \mathbb{R}^N$, updated via the hidden state $z_t \in \mathbb{R}^N$. The time step constant τ controls the update and it is a hyper-parameter of RON. The part inside the hyperbolic tangent σ is the same as in an ESN. The hyper-parameters τ and the spectral norm of W , are especially important to bias the RON model towards the identity mapping and provide stable dynamics [3]. Moreover, RON introduces a per-unit damping term $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and a per-unit stiffness term $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^N$ that are combined with the hidden states through an element-wise multiplication \odot . The set of values of ε , and γ , directly affects the distribution of eigenvalues of the Jacobian of RON, thus regulating the linear stability properties of RON and allowing for a wide plethora of dynamical behaviours [3]. RON follows the principles of reservoir computing, as it keeps all matrices fixed and it initializes them like in the ESN. The linear readout takes as input h_t and projects it into the output space. The readout is trained in closed-form.

We are interested in sparse topologies of W for RON. Fully-connected reservoirs, where each recurrent unit is possibly connected to all the other recurrent units, is one of the most common options used when building a reservoir computing model. However, fully-connected reservoirs might induce unnecessary coupling in the recurrent unit, resulting in extra computation. In our paper, we exploit some sparse forms of W , properly introduced in Section 3.

3 Sparse RON Topologies

We designed 6 different sparse reservoir topologies that we applied to the RON model, as well as the Leaky ESN. In all the following, we assume a recurrent state-update matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$. We set a sparsity level of $P\%$, where $P = 0$ corresponds to a fully-connected reservoir matrix. In building sparse topologies of RON, we prioritized structures that are more prone to physical implementations. A fully-connected network of N oscillators has N^2 interconnections. This prevents RON from mechanical implementations at a large scale. Moreover, often in nature neural networks are characterised by local connections forming relatively sparse topologies. One solution to model local connections while tuning the sparsity of the network is to promote a band-like diagonal structure in the recurrent matrix W , suppressing far-from-diagonal connections.

For this reason, apart from the Sparse Orthogonal case (as discussed below), in all the other cases we sparsify the recurrent matrix W zeroing-out diagonal elements starting with the most far from the main diagonal and proceeding towards the main diagonal until the desired sparsity level is reached. The spectral radius of W is then scaled accordingly, following the principles described in Section 2.

Sparse Orthogonal. (or simply orthogonal). We randomly initialize W uniformly in $[0, 1]$. Then, we compute the QR factorization of W and we take the matrix $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ to be our orthogonal matrix (note that the elements of Q will also be negative). However, Q is a dense, fully-connected matrix. To enforce sparsity, we randomly zero-out $\lfloor \frac{P \times N}{100} \rfloor$ rows of Q . In practice, we perform the matrix multiplication $W = IQ$, where I is a $N \times N$ identity matrix with P elements of the diagonal set to 0. The elements of I to be zeroed-out are randomly selected.

Lower triangular. we randomly initialize W as a lower-triangular matrix where each element is sampled uniformly in $[-1, 1]$. According to the sparsity level P , and starting from the bottom, we remove a certain number of “lower” diagonals, where $j < i$ (j indexes the columns of W and i indexes its rows). A lower triangular matrix has already a base sparsity level of roughly 50%, as half of its value are zeroed-out. Further removing diagonals increases its sparsity. For example, for $W \in \mathbb{R}^{100 \times 100}$ and $P = 90\%$, the resulting matrix will only have 10 active diagonals in the lower part (including the main diagonal). We zero-out $\lfloor \frac{P \times N}{100} \rfloor$ lower diagonals, starting from the last one (which only includes the first value of the last row of W) and going up. Lower triangular matrices are associated with feed-forward architectures. A schematic example of the sparse lower triangular topology is depicted in Fig. 1.

Band. we randomly initialize W uniformly in $[-1, 1]$. Then, starting from the top and bottom and proceeding towards the main diagonal, we remove the upper ($j > i$) and lower ($j < i$) diagonals, up until reaching the desired level of sparsity. The resulting matrix has zero everywhere except that in a bandwidth spread around the main diagonal. The width of the bandwidth is inversely proportional to the sparsity level. A schematic example of the sparse band topology is depicted in Fig. 2.

Toeplitz. we first generate a band matrix as defined above. Then, we constraint the entries on each diagonal to have the same value. Toeplitz matrices describe linear convolutional operators. A schematic example of the sparse Toeplitz topology is depicted in Fig. 3.

Ring. we create a simple cycle (or ring) matrix by filling with 1s the main sub-diagonal of W as well as the last element of the first row. The rest of the elements are zero. The simple cycle matrix has a fixed sparsity: the only non-zero elements are $N - 1$ ones in the main sub-diagonal and the one in the last place of the first row, for a total of N non-zero elements. Therefore, the sparsity level is $100 \frac{N^2 - N}{N^2} \% = 100(1 - \frac{1}{N})\%$. As the name suggests, in a ring topology each unit is connected only with one other unit and the connections form a ring across the units. A schematic example of the ring topology is depicted in Fig. 4.

Circulant. we randomly initialise C real numbers in $[-1, 1]$, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_C . We define a circulant matrix with sparsity $100(1 - \frac{C}{N})\%$

by defining $(W)_{i+s,i} = r_s$, for $i = 0, \dots, N - 1$, and $s = 1, \dots, C$, where the index $i + s$ is intended modulo N . Thus, the circulant structure defined in this way is a natural generalisation of the ring topology that we recover as particular case when $C = 1$. In fact, when $C = 1$, then we have $(W)_{i+1,i} = r_1$ for $i = 0, \dots, N - 2$, i.e. the entire subdiagonal, and $(W)_{0,N-1} = r_1$, i.e. the top right corner. A schematic example of the sparse circulant topology is depicted in Fig. 5. A similar circulant architecture has been studied in [14], but there the authors focused on adding jumps (connections) of a fixed length in the ring topology, while here we consider all possible jumps within a given length defined by a predetermined sparsity level.

Full. for comparison, we also use a fully-connected W ($P = 0\%$) randomly initialized in $[-2, 2]$. Note that the topology denoted as “Full” does not necessarily correspond to a different topology with sparsity $P = 0\%$. In fact, the other topologies are initialized in a different way than the Full topology, where the recurrent weight matrix W has no particular structure. For example, the Orthogonal topology with $P = 0\%$ does not correspond to the Full topology, as the Orthogonal topology constraints W to be orthogonal. A similar reasoning applies to the other topologies as well.

We study in detail the performance of the aforementioned topologies at different levels of sparsity and for different datasets.

Figure 1: A 10×10 lower triangular matrix. In black the non-zero entries. The corresponding topology is a feed-forward architecture with the addition of self-loops corresponding to the main diagonal entries. The connections are i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $(-1, 1)$. Then the matrix is rescaled to a desired spectral radius. The sparsity level in the picture is 66%.

4 Experiments

We chose 3 different benchmarks that are widely used for sequence processing tasks. Two of them, sequential MNIST and Adiac, are sequence classification tasks. The other, Mackey-Glass, is a chaotic time-series forecasting task.

For classification tasks, we compute the output of the models by feeding the last hidden state (i.e., the hidden state computed on the final time step of each sequence) to the linear readout layer. The readout outputs a probability for each candidate class and the class

Figure 2: A 10×10 band matrix. In black the non-zero entries. The corresponding topology is characterised by bidirectional flow, and self-loops corresponding to the main diagonal entries. The connections are i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $(-1, 1)$. Then the matrix is rescaled to a desired spectral radius. The sparsity level in the picture is 56%.

Figure 3: A 10×10 (band) Toeplitz matrix. The non-zero entries are coloured. Same colours represent same real values. In the case depicted there are effectively just 5 different real values, i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $(-1, 1)$, disposed in 5 different diagonals. Then the matrix is rescaled to a desired spectral radius. The corresponding topology is similar to the band topology with the additional constraints given by the diagonals. The sparsity level in the picture is 56%.

with the largest probability is selected as the final prediction. For the time-series forecasting task, the readout returns an output for each hidden state computed by the reservoir at each time step.

We compare the results obtained by RON and Leaky ESN with a fully-trained LSTM model. The LSTM recurrent weights are fully connected and trained via backpropagation through time.

Sequential MNIST. sMNIST creates sequences out of each MNIST image by taking it one pixel at a time. The objective is to classify each sequence into the correct digit class. We obtained a dataset with 57,000 training examples, 3,000 validation examples and 10,000 test examples. Each example is a univariate sequence with 784 time step. Given the length of the sequences, sMNIST is meant to test

Figure 4: A 10×10 simple cycle matrix. The only non-zero entries are those in the subdiagonal and on the top right corner, and all of them are the same real value. Such unique real value is rescaled to a desired spectral radius. This connection matrix forms a ring topology. The sparsity level in the picture is 90%.

Figure 5: A 10×10 circulant matrix. The non-zero entries are coloured. Same colours represent same real values. In the case depicted there are effectively just 3 different real values, i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $(-1, 1)$. Then the matrix is rescaled to a desired spectral radius. The corresponding topology can be represented as an annular network. Note the lack of self-loops in this topology. This architecture generalises the ring topology. The sparsity level in the picture is 70%.

the long-term memory of recurrent models, as well as their ability to exploit the memory to correctly classify the example.

Adiac. Adiac¹ is a sequence classification dataset where each sequence is univariate and has 176 time steps. Adiac is a real-world dataset that requires to recognise (among 37 classes) a unicellular algae from thresholded images converted into time-series. Therefore, the model performs multiclass classification. We divided the dataset into a training, validation and test dataset with 270, 120 and 391 sequences, respectively.

¹Adiac taken from timeseriesclassification.com

Mackey-Glass. MG [8] is a popular univariate time-series forecasting dataset for chaotic dynamical systems. The time-series is generated out of the Mackey-Glass equations. The objective is, for each time step, to predict the 84-th next state [8]. We split the dataset into a single sequence of 4,196 time steps for the training set, 2,416 time steps for the validation set and 2,416 time steps for the test set. During training, all models use a washout of 200 time steps: the model processes the sequences but its predictions are not taken into account in the training phase. This is a common procedure to “warm up” the reservoir. The metrics used to test the performance are the average accuracy for sMNIST and Adiac classification tasks, and the normalized root mean squared error (NRMSE) for the Mackey-Glass task. Given a target sequence $y = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_T)$ with T time steps and a predicted output sequence $\hat{y} = (\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_T)$ with the same number of time steps, we compute the NRMSE as following:

$$\text{NRMSE}(\hat{y}, y) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^T y_i^2 + 10^{-9}}}, \quad (3)$$

where the small constant 10^{-9} is added to ensure positive denominator. A model predicting the expected target for each time step would score a NRMSE of 0.

4.1 Model selection

Unless otherwise noted, we used 100 units in the reservoir. For the grid search on the validation set of each dataset, we considered $\gamma \in \{2, 10, 20\}$, $\gamma_r \in \{2, 10\}$, $\epsilon \in \{2, 10, 20\}$, $\epsilon_r \in \{2, 10\}$, $\rho \in \{0.9, 9\}$, $\nu \in \{0.1, 1, 10\}$. The hyperparameters γ_r and ϵ_r denote, respectively, the ranges of heterogeneity of stiffness and dampening of the oscillators in the reservoir. In essence, once selected center values γ , ϵ and range values γ_r , ϵ_r for stiffness and dampening, we generate oscillators with random stiffness values i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $[\gamma - \frac{\gamma_r}{2}, \gamma + \frac{\gamma_r}{2}]$, and random dampening values i.i.d. uniformly sampled in $[\epsilon - \frac{\epsilon_r}{2}, \epsilon + \frac{\epsilon_r}{2}]$. The RON’s time-scale τ has been selected in $\{0.042, 0.42, 4.2\}$ for sMNIST, in $\{0.01, 0.1, 1\}$ for Adiac and in $\{0.017, 0.17, 1.7\}$ for Mackey-Glass.

For the Leaky ESN we considered $\rho \in \{0.9, 0.99, 0.999, 9\}$, $\alpha \in \{0.001, 0.01, 0.1\}$, $\nu \in \{0.1, 1, 10\}$, while, each element of the input-to-hidden matrix W^{in} and the hidden-to-hidden matrix W is uniformly sampled in $[-2, 2]$. The bias is uniformly sampled in $[-1, 1]$.

We repeated the same grid search when scaling up the number of hidden units.

We set the LSTM to use 10 hidden units, to roughly match the number of parameters of RON and Leaky ESN. The LSTM is trained with Adam with a learning rate of 2×10^{-3} , found by model selection.

Mean and standard deviation is computed on test over 5 different random seeds. The code to reproduce all the experiments is available at https://github.com/AndreaCossu/RON_topology.

4.2 Results

We found that all RON configurations surpass the performance of Leaky ESN on all three benchmarks by a significant margin, across all levels of sparsity and over different numbers of hidden units.

Due to the training of recurrent parameters, the training time of LSTM is one order of magnitude larger than the one of RON

and Leaky ESN, which are optimized in closed form. We observed that, in a regime with a few parameters, the LSTM under-performs with respect to both Leaky ESN and RON (as showed by Tables 1, 2, 3). When increasing the number of units up to 50, we managed to achieve an average accuracy on sMNIST of about 83%, which jumps to 96% for 256 units. For 1,000 hidden units, the LSTM surpasses RON and Leaky ESN of around 3% on sMNIST. On Adiac, even with hundreds of units, RON and Leaky ESN always outperform the LSTM. This is due to the low number of examples per class in Adiac. Under this regime, reservoir computing models show an advantage with respect to fully-trained models. On MG, the reservoir computing models always outperform LSTM, even when increasing the number of units. In fact, reservoir computing models are particularly well suited for chaotic time series forecasting. To provide a fair comparison, all tables report results for our experimental setup where RON and Leaky ESN use 100 units and, to keep the same number of trainable parameters, LSTM uses 10.

We observed that RON-based reservoir computing models retain a strong performance even when the number of randomized parameters is greatly reduced. Table 1 shows the average accuracy on sMNIST across multiple levels of sparsity. Even when pruning 80% of the connections in the hidden-to-hidden matrix W , both RON and Leaky ESN achieve a good performance. However, Leaky ESN shows a monotonically decreasing accuracy trend as sparsity increases. This is not the case for RON with sparse topologies.

Compared to the full RON, where W is a fully-connected matrix, all the sparse variants remain competitive. In particular, *circulant RON* and *band RON* do not show any performance decrease when pruning 80% of the hidden-to-hidden weights. Interestingly, *circulant RON* and *band RON* with sparsity levels greater than or equal to 40% can surpass the fully connected RON variant. The other variants (the lower triangular, the orthogonal, and the Toeplitz RON) lose a few points for high sparsity levels (60–80%), but they still surpass the Leaky ESN. The ring RON, a popular topology borrowed from the ESN literature, performs on par with the full RON. This confirms the effectiveness of ring-like architectures in classification problems with hundreds of time steps.

Adiac is a challenging dataset due to the low number of examples. However, sequences are much shorter than sMNIST. Therefore, unlike sMNIST, the model is not required to show long-term memory properties but rather an effective input-output mapping. Table 2 shows that, on Adiac, the performance of Leaky ESN slowly decreases as the sparsity level increases. RON, instead, is more robust to different sparsity levels. The only exception is the lower triangular RON, whose performance decreases from around 71% with 50% sparsity to 68% with 90% sparsity. Interestingly, on the Adiac task the Orthogonal variant with 80% sparsity almost matches the full RON. Similarly to the sMNIST classification task, the circulant RON exhibits strong performance also on Adiac, suggesting this topology as promising for classification tasks in general. Although, the full RON obtains the best score on Adiac, the Toeplitz, Orthogonal, and Circulant topologies are able to closely approach the full RON performance even with sparsity levels greater or equal than 40%.

Up to now, we focused on sequence classification datasets, where the objective is to predict the target class given the entire class. Nevertheless, recurrent models and reservoir computing models in particular, are especially powerful in time-series forecasting task.

Table 1: Final accuracy on sMNIST test set for different levels of sparsity. Mean and std over 5 runs. Best hyper-parameters computed for each sparsity separately. Full and ring topologies have a fixed sparsity level (0% for full, 99% for ring). In bold the best performance for each level of sparsity. The best performance overall is underlined.

Accuracy (%)		sMNIST				
LSTM		45.1 ± 0.1				
Full		86.2 ± 1.5				
Ring		85.3 ± 2.5				
Sparsity	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	
Orthogonal	86.3 ± 2.2	82.1 ± 2.1	79.7 ± 2.0	85.4 ± 2.0	81.4 ± 1.3	
Band	85.4 ± 1.3	85.5 ± 1.2	86.2 ± 0.9	85.4 ± 1.7	84.6 ± 0.8	
Toeplitz	86.6 ± 0.9	81.7 ± 0.5	85.4 ± 1.6	83.0 ± 1.7	81.3 ± 3.0	
Circulant	84.9 ± 1.7	85.6 ± 1.0	<u>86.7 ± 0.5</u>	83.6 ± 1.2	86.6 ± 0.6	
Leaky ESN	79.8 ± 0.1	79.6 ± 0.1	78.3 ± 0.1	77.6 ± 0.1	74.3 ± 0.1	
Sparsity	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	
Lower Triangular	84.3 ± 1.8	83.9 ± 1.1	84.2 ± 1.5	83.6 ± 3.0	84.1 ± 1.4	

Table 2: Final accuracy on Adiac test set for different levels of sparsity. Mean and std over 5 runs. Best hyper-parameters computed for each sparsity separately. Full and ring topologies have a fixed sparsity level (0% for full, 99% for ring). In bold the best performance for each level of sparsity. The best performance overall is underlined.

Accuracy (%)		Adiac				
LSTM		3.8 ± 0.2				
Full		<u>72.7 ± 1.0</u>				
Ring		71.6 ± 1.2				
Sparsity	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	
Orthogonal	68.1 ± 3.2	70.7 ± 1.3	71.2 ± 0.6	69.9 ± 1.0	71.4 ± 1.7	
Band	67.5 ± 2.9	69.8 ± 1.8	68.9 ± 1.6	69.3 ± 1.0	69.8 ± 2.1	
Toeplitz	69.9 ± 1.4	70.6 ± 0.6	69.3 ± 1.0	71.4 ± 1.8	69.3 ± 1.4	
Circulant	69.8 ± 1.8	71.6 ± 1.1	72.2 ± 0.9	70.3 ± 1.7	70.2 ± 1.1	
Leaky ESN	68.5 ± 2.7	67.1 ± 1.6	67.5 ± 1.8	66.0 ± 1.1	65.8 ± 2.8	
Sparsity	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	
Lower Triangular	71.4 ± 1.7	71.4 ± 2.0	69.2 ± 0.6	71.3 ± 1.5	68.6 ± 1.7	

Table 3 reports the NRMSE computed on the Mackey-Glass task. In Mackey-Glass, the gap between RON and the Leaky ESN is even larger than in the other benchmarks. The NRMSE of RON is smaller than half of the NRMSE of Leaky ESN across all sparsity levels. Again, the lower triangular RON shows a small decrease in performance as the sparsity level increases. The other sparse topologies enjoy a robust performance with low variation between one sparsity level and another. The *band* RON results the clear winner on the Mackey-Glass task, almost over all sparsity levels considered. Surprisingly, the band topology with 80% sparsity achieves an NRMSE score almost halved compared to the full RON while displaying a smaller standard deviation.

All the results presented so far may be questioned by the fact that the reservoir computing models employ a relatively low number of hidden units. In turn, increasing the sparsity percentage may result

in a relatively small number of additional dropped connections in W . To account for this effect, we ran additional experiments by increasing the number of hidden units in RON and Leaky ESN. Beside the experiments presented above with 100 units, we report the performance of all models with 500, 1,000 and 2,000 hidden units on sMNIST (Table 4) and Mackey-Glass (Table 5). We did not run the same set of experiments on Adiac, since the main challenge of Adiac is to learn from a limited number of examples. Therefore, reservoirs with thousands of units would only over-fit to the examples in the dataset. For this family of experiments, we always set the sparsity level to a large value, namely 80%, in order to be able to properly compare all the models.

On sMNIST (Table 4), we see that adding more units quickly increases the final performance of all models. Leaky ESN jumps from 74% of accuracy with 100 units to 88%. It is worth observing

Table 3: Final NRMSE on Mackey-Glass test set for different levels of sparsity. Mean and std over 5 runs. Best hyper-parameters computed for each sparsity separately. Full and ring topologies have a fixed sparsity level (0% for full, 99% for ring). In bold the best performance for each level of sparsity. The best performance overall is underlined.

NRMSE		Mackey-Glass				
LSTM		0.34 ± 0.01				
Full		0.19 ± 0.06				
Ring		0.16 ± 0.03				
Sparsity	0%	20%	40%	60%	80%	
Orthogonal	0.16 ± 0.09	0.23 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.12	0.15 ± 0.04	0.15 ± 0.03	
Band	0.14 ± 0.03	0.12 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.06	<u>0.11 ± 0.02</u>	
Toeplitz	0.13 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.02	0.13 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.02	0.12 ± 0.02	
Circulant	0.15 ± 0.02	0.12 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.01	0.13 ± 0.02	
Leaky ESN	0.37 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.03	0.38 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.01	0.37 ± 0.02	
Sparsity	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	
Lower Triangular	0.16 ± 0.01	0.16 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.01	

Table 4: Final accuracy on sMNIST test set for different numbers of hidden neurons and 80% sparsity (apart from Ring where sparsity is ≥ 99%, and Full where sparsity is 0%). Mean and std over 5 runs. Best hyper-parameters computed for each configuration separately. In bold the best performance for each hidden size. The best performance overall is underlined.

sMNIST Accuracy (%)	100	500	1,000	2,000
Full	86.2 ± 1.5	93.6 ± 0.4	95.5 ± 0.3	96.4 ± 0.2
Ring	85.3 ± 2.5	94.0 ± 0.1	95.3 ± 0.2	95.6 ± 0.1
Orthogonal	81.4 ± 1.3	92.3 ± 0.3	93.5 ± 0.5	93.2 ± 0.2
Band	84.6 ± 0.8	92.7 ± 0.3	95.2 ± 0.2	<u>96.4 ± 0.1</u>
Toeplitz	81.3 ± 3.0	91.3 ± 0.4	93.4 ± 0.2	94.3 ± 0.1
Circulant	86.6 ± 0.6	92.7 ± 0.3	93.7 ± 0.2	94.4 ± 0.1
Leaky ESN	74.3 ± 0.1	83.3 ± 0.1	85.8 ± 0.1	88.1 ± 0.1

Table 5: Final NRMSE on Mackey-Glass test set for different numbers of hidden neurons and 80% sparsity (apart from Ring where sparsity is ≥ 99%, and Full where sparsity is 0%). Mean and std over 5 runs. Best hyper-parameters computed for each configuration separately. In bold the best performance for each hidden size. The best performance overall is underlined.

MG NRMSE	100	500	1,000	2,000
Full	0.19 ± 0.06	0.15 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01
Ring	0.16 ± 0.03	0.07 ± 0.03	0.05 ± 0.02	<u>0.03 ± 0.01</u>
Orthogonal	0.15 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.04	0.08 ± 0.07	0.13 ± 0.12
Band	0.11 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.03	0.15 ± 0.11	0.09 ± 0.01
Toeplitz	0.12 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.04	0.07 ± 0.01
Circulant	0.13 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.02
Leaky ESN	0.37 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.01

that RON models of just 100 units can surpass Leaky ESNs of $\times 10$ number of neurons on sMNIST. Albeit circulant RON demonstrated the strongest performance on sMNIST with 100 units, when scaling up the reservoir size the *band* RON architecture surpasses all the other considered models. Still, all RON models greatly surpass Leaky ESN: the best-performing RONs are the full RON and the band RON, scoring over 96% on test. All the other RON variants are all above

93% test accuracy, while Leaky ESN merely touches 88%. These results show that the small amount of hidden units used in our first set of experiments did not introduce a confounding factor on the sparsity effect. Even with 20 times as many units, sparse topologies with RON can achieve a comparable performance with respect to their fully-connected version.

This is also confirmed on Mackey-Glass (Table 5), where the NRMSE of all models is halved when switching from 100 to 2,000 hidden units. Again, all RON models surpass the Leaky ESN by a large margin. Here the gap widens since RON models of just 100 units can abundantly surpass Leaky ESNs of $\times 20$ number of neurons on Mackey-Glass. Similarly to sMNIST, also on Mackey-Glass we observe the optimal topology to change when scaling up the reservoir size. In fact, although band RON demonstrated the strongest performance on Mackey-Glass with 100 units, when increasing the number of units the ring architecture surpasses all the other considered models. Remarkably, *ring RON* reaches a staggering $3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ NRMSE, five times smaller than a Leaky ESN with the same number of 2000 units. Therefore, we can conclude that increasing the number of hidden units in RON causes a corresponding increase in the performance, preserving both the robustness against large sparsity levels and the advantage with respect to the Leaky ESN.

5 Conclusion and Future Works

We introduced and studied the behaviour of different sparse topologies in RON, an oscillators-based recurrent neural network inspired by reservoir computing. We formally defined 6 sparse topologies for the reservoir of RON: the sparse orthogonal, the lower triangular, the ring, the band, the Toeplitz and the circulant. The topologies show different connections patterns between units. Ring topology aside, all the other topologies can be customized by choosing a desired level of sparsity (i.e., by removing connections in the hidden-to-hidden matrix W). The rationale behind our sparsification methodology is to prioritise local connections to ease the physical implementations of these models. Our experiments show that sparse RON topologies are very effective in sequence classification tasks, both in a long-range setting as well as in a tasks with few examples. Moreover, all sparse versions of RON exhibit excellent performance on chaotic time-series forecasting. This behaviour is confirmed even when scaling up the number of hidden units in the reservoir, thus also increasing the amount of dropped connections. For example, by using 2,000 hidden units we were able to achieve more than 96% test accuracy on sMNIST with only 20% of active connections (80% sparsity), and improving $\times 5$ over Leaky ESN on Mackey-Glass with only 0.005% of active connections (99.95% sparsity). We observed that all topologies scale well to high sparsity values. Overall, the final performance was always comparable to (if not better than) the performance of a fully-connected network without sparsity. Remarkably, sparse RON topologies surpassed the performance of sparse Leaky ESN in all experiments, even by a large margin.

Our experiments suggest the circulant (including ring) and the band as the most promising topologies. Moreover, it emerges that the specific topology can significantly improve the performance while massively dropping the number of possible connections (even more than 99.9%), and that, in general, large sparsity levels are well tolerated by the RON model. This is a positive result indicating the possibility to physically implement RON, where the oscillators are coupled just with their neighbours, and having the chance to outperform fully connected digital alternatives. Another interesting aspect emerged is that for a predetermined sparsity level the optimal topology might depend on the reservoir size.

The opportunity to leverage on sparse topologies in oscillatory-based recurrent models like RON opens up the possibility of implementation of such networks in real-world applications. One of the common problems when considering neuromorphic / physical implementation of neural networks is that all units in a layer are fully connected to all units in the next layer. Recurrent neural networks with a single layer suffer from the same issue since the units within the same layer are fully-connected.

Developing sparse topologies allows to simplify the physical implementation of the model and allows for more flexibility in its development. Ad-hoc sparse connections can follow the constraints coming from the hardware substrate. For oscillatory-based models, it is unlikely to build a fully-connected network of thousands of oscillators outside a computer simulation. With our work, we showed that: 1) oscillators-based models like RON do not always need thousands of units, but they can work well even with only 100 hidden units; 2) RON can prune the vast majority of the recurrent connections without affecting its predictive performance.

Since RON follows the reservoir computing paradigm, we do not need to train the recurrent connections after the model is realised on a hardware substrate. This also gets rid of the on-device training issue, which still plagues all fully-trainable models like the LSTM when it comes to their physical implementation.

Overall, RON looks like a compelling candidate for a physical implementation, due to both its computational efficiency (no training required on the recurrent component) and its effectiveness when equipped with very sparse topologies.

Acknowledgments

This work has been partially supported by the EU EIC project EMERGE (Grant No. 101070918) and by NEURONE, a project funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (PRIN 20229JRTZA).

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